

Modeling the Global Citation Network using the Scalable Agent-based Simulator for Citation Analysis with Recency-emphasized Sampling (SASCA-ReS)

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Abstract

The global science literature, represented as a network with articles as nodes and citations as edges, is a rich artifact for scientometric studies. The structure of this network depends on its count of nodes and distribution of edges. We are interested in how the network has evolved from its origin to its present structure. Since extant theories of citation do not offer much in the way of quantitative explanation, we use a modeling approach that generates synthetic networks. Specifically, we have developed an idealized agent-based model of citations (SASCA-ReS) that can generate synthetic networks of size over 200 million nodes, which is comparable with the size of today's science literature. This model allows us to reason in an artificial world and to identify patterns of citation that may explain real-world scenarios. We report results from simulations under this model with different parameter settings and at various scales to explore counterfactual and hypothetical scenarios.

Keywords: agent-based models, citation networks, scientometrics

1 Introduction

We conservatively estimate the body of scientific literature to be in the order of 100-300 million articles [1–3] today: a remarkable increase of around six orders of magnitude over 360 years since 1655 when the first scientific journal published less than a hundred articles in its inaugural year [4]. Representing this collection as a citation network with nodes (articles) connected by directed edges (citations) [5–8] enables scientometric studies from historical, epistemological, sociological, and graph-theoretic perspectives. Within this area of investigation, we seek to understand how the citations made by authors influence the structure of large citation networks. Additionally, given the incentives for authors to be well-cited, we are interested in strategies that influence the accumulation of citations at the level of an individual article.

Preceding theories of citation offer some insight into the motivations of researchers that translate into citation behavior [9–13]. These motivations can be coarsely grouped into normative and rhetorical types, with the additional motivation of malpractice being worthy of mention today [14, 15]. However, motivations are not easily measured and are unlikely to be mutually exclusive. It seems more likely that each citation made by an author comprises multiple motivations that vary with time and context. Thus, quantitatively analyzing motivations is challenging. Nevertheless, citation behavior has been modeled on stylized normative and rhetorical behavior, although at a small scale and for the purpose of studying effects on “community health” [16].

An alternative to quantifying motivations is to construct generative models that are based on observed patterns of citation and study growth patterns under these models. In this respect, mathematical models of network growth [17–19] have been proposed that incorporate randomness, preferential attachment [20, 21], recency (immediacy) [5, 22], as well as fitness (epistemic quality) [23, 24].

In a complementary approach, we have previously developed two idealized agent-based models (ABMs) that enable simulations of network growth: PyABM [25], written in Python, and its successor, SASCA-s [26] (Scalable Agent-based Simulator for Citation Analysis with sampling), written in C++. Both models take a citation network as input and produce a larger citation network as output, which results from letting the random process operate over time steps.

During a simulation, batches of agents are generated in time-steps of a year. Each agent is created by vertex copying [27, 28] a randomly selected node in the network, which is termed the agent’s generator. The agent is then assigned a quota of citations to make, which is randomly drawn from a real-world distribution. Once an agent satisfies this quota, it persists in the network and serves as a target of citation by other agents.

The basis for selecting a target to cite is a composite formulation of the target’s features, its distance from the generator node, and the agent’s “citation phenotype”, which is a weighted combination of its bias towards preferential attachment, recency, and fitness. In the PyABM model, each new agent evaluates every other node in the network before selecting nodes to cite. This approach becomes expensive as the network grows and affects scalability, essentially limiting PyABM simulations to 1-2 million nodes.

SASCA-s addresses this limitation by requiring each new agent to score only a random sample of nodes within the 2-hop neighborhood of its generator (nodes at a distance of 1 or 2). Combined with the performance of a compiled language, this sampling approach allows SASCA-s to scale to more than 100,000,000 nodes. A third generation of the initial model, SASCA-ReS (Scalable Agent-based Simulator for Citation Analysis with Recency-emphasized Sampling) improved recency modeling by enforcing the distribution of citations made by each agent to produce a good fit to an empirically derived “recency table” that we computed from a citation network. This modification to SASCA-ReS provides the same scalability advantage of SASCA-s but with a better match to the several empirical properties of citation networks. The results presented in this manuscript are from the use of SASCA-ReS.

We stress that SASCA-ReS is an idealized model in which reality is not replicated. Of the various ways in which ABMs can be used [29], we designed the model to support reasoning rather than to replicate real-world observations. This design offers advantages in terms of model parsimony and computational cost. Thus, the scenarios illuminated by the simulations reported below are *exploratory* and may or may not map to corresponding mechanisms of network growth in the real-world. Apart from the small number of variables, we have made additional simplifying assumptions. First, that every agent represents an article written by a single author and that no author has contributed more than one article to the network. Second, that we do not consider disciplinary habits or trends in citation behavior over time.

In the sections that follow, we report results from varied simulations resulting in networks ranging from just over a million nodes to greater than 150 million nodes. We focus both on network structure and the accumulation of citations by individual nodes.

2 Materials and Methods

Throughout this manuscript, `in_degree` is used to refer to citations *received* by a node while `out_degree` is synonymous with citations *made* to other nodes (references).

2.1 Data

Simulations shown in this manuscript used one of three different seed networks as input: (i) the Stahl-Johnstone (*sj*) network consisting of 491,532 nodes and 899,051 edges, which is derived from a real-world network from the biomedical literature and has been previously described in [25], (ii) the *sj_er* network, which is an Erdős-Rényi network modelled after the *sj* network, and (iii) the *g10x10* network, which is a lattice network with 100 nodes arranged in a square grid with edges directed from one corner to the opposite corner in an acyclic pattern. The *sj_er* and *g10x10* were generated using the `sample_gnm` model in the R `igraph` package [30] and any nodes without edges were dropped.

Three model-generated networks are reported in this article varying in size from approximately 14M nodes to 161M (Table 2). The first two (`abm14` and `abm76`) were seeded with *sj*, the third (`abm161`) was seeded with the lattice graph; motivated by the

	# nodes	# edges	Reference
<i>sj</i>	491,532	899,051	[26]
<i>sj_er</i>	479,027	899,051	[26]
<i>g10x10</i>	100	180	

Table 1 Seed networks *sj*: the Stahl-Johnstone network derived from the biomedical literature [25]; *sj_er* is an Erdős-Rényi network modelled after *sj*; and *g10x10*: a lattice network of 100 nodes

prior use of a two-dimensional epistemic grid [31, 32] and to approximate the number of publications in the inaugural year (1665) of [4]. For the two smaller networks, *abm14* and *abm76*, the *sj* dataset was used as a starting point and the simulation allowed to proceed for 85 and 128 years respectively at a growth rate of 4.0125%. For *abm161*, the year of each node in the lattice was set to 1655, the fitness of each node was set to 1 (out of a possible range of 1 – 1000), and a constant growth of growth rate 4.0125% was applied for a simulation that lasted 360 years. For the first 150 years of this simulation, a normally distributed out_degree distribution ranging from 1 – 10 was used, after which it was exchanged for a PubMed derived out_degree distribution described in [26] that reflects more modern citation rates. During scalability testing, we also generated a network with 217,839,850 nodes and 9,390,741,826 edges using 128 cores and 450GB of RAM (Supplemental Materials: S4). Comparable real-world networks referenced (Table 2) have been previously described: the Curated Exosome Network or CEN (*cen*) and Open Citations (*oc*) network with 13,989,436 and 75,025,194 nodes respectively were described in [33] and the network extracted from Open Alex data (*oa*) with 111,453,719 nodes was described in [34].

	# nodes	# edges	network	generation runtime
1	160,714,032	6,940,630,767	<i>abm161</i>	< 71hrs
2	75,598,213	3,245,034,596	<i>abm76</i>	< 4 hrs
3	13,926,219	581,472,876	<i>abm14</i>	< 30 min
4	111,453,719	2,148,788,148	<i>oa</i>	n.a.
5	75,025,194	1,363,303,678	<i>oc</i>	n.a.
6	13,989,436	92,051,051	<i>cen</i>	n.a.

Table 2 Summary statistics of simulated and real-world networks. Network sizes are shown for simulated networks (rows 1-3) and real-world networks (rows 4-6); we also show the time used to generate the simulated networks. The networks *oa* and *oc* are derived from the OpenAlex and Open Citations collections respectively [35], and *cen* [8] refers to the Curated Exosome Network, which is derived from the biomedical literature.

2.2 SASCA-ReS

Here we describe SASCA-ReS in more detail with additional information available in Supplementary Materials (S1). The code for SASCA-ReS is freely available from Github [36].

Each agent in a simulation is created by vertex copying from a randomly selected node in the network, termed the “generator”. When created, an agent is assigned a quota of citations to make that is randomly drawn from a real-world distribution of reference counts (see `out_degree` distribution below) and randomly assigned a fitness value ranging from 1-1000 that is drawn from a synthetic power law distribution. Thus, every agent has the following attributes: (i) a time stamp for when it was created (year), (ii) its fitness, and (iii) a quota of citations (its `out_degree`) to make as attributes. Within a time-step each agent makes citations independently of other agents and the network is updated at the end of the time step. The duration of simulation and number of agents added each year are controlled by two environment parameters. These are set by the user and comprise the duration of simulation in years and growth rate, which is a percentage of the number of nodes in the network. Overall, the design of SASCA-ReS incorporates a mid-level modeling approach [37] where parameter settings for recency and `out_degree` quota are drawn from real-world data in order to focus on *more likely* rather than *formally possible* outcomes.

A parameter α defines the fraction of an agent’s citation quota (`out_degree`) within the 2-hop neighborhood that go to the 1-hop neighborhood of its generator; thus, $\alpha = 1$ means that all its citations are made to nodes in the 1-hop neighborhood once a required citation to the generator and a small quota representing idiosyncratic citations [38, p. 203] are made to nodes selected by uniform random sampling from the entire network. Additionally, 12% of the agents are randomly selected to make a single citation to another agent created in the same year. Thus, an agent’s quota is divided across its citations to the generator node, the distance 1 and distance 2 neighborhoods of the generator, the possible same-year citation, and its idiosyncratic component. A special case is the *noalpha* option where the citation quota is satisfied by sampling from the the 2-hop neighborhood.

Based on references in publications in a real-world citation network [8], we computed a recency table (Supplementary Materials, S5) that defines the expected fraction of its citation quota that an agent will make to papers that were published n years ago, for each $n \geq 0$. This recency table is derived from the cell biology literature but can be replaced by any other user-defined table. Similarly we have constructed an `out_degree` distribution array from recent PubMed data, which is described in [26]. Given the `out_degree` quota and recency table, we derive the expected distribution of citations to papers from a given year for each agent. Since achieving this distribution exactly is not always possible, we have implemented an approach that redistributes the `out_degree` when necessary to publications in adjacent years.

Since recency is now managed externally, as described above, the citation phenotype for an agent is a weighted composite of bias towards two attributes—preferential attachment and fitness. In contrast, the citation phenotypes for SASCA-s and PyABM also included a weight for recency, which is not relevant for SASCA-ReS. Thus, in SASCA-ReS, the phenotype for an agent node is composed of the weights it attaches to

preferential attachment and fitness, where the weights add up to 1.0. Agent phenotypes may be randomly assigned (*ra*) from a uniform distribution of possible phenotypes or fixed such that every agent has exactly the same phenotype.

Finally, like SASCA-s, SASCA-ReS only samples and scores at most 20,000 nodes in the 2-hop neighborhood of its generator node (specifically, it samples and scores at most 10,000 node at distance 1 and 10,000 nodes at distance 2 from its generator). As noted above, any nodes from outside the 2-hop neighborhood that are cited as part of the idiosyncratic component are randomly selected without being scored. In this way, SASCA-ReS also samples at most 20,000 nodes in the network, all of which are in the 2-hop neighborhood of its generator node, while obtaining a better fit to the observed recency distribution of citation networks.

2.3 Simulations

SASCA-ReS simulations are conducted by passing in four input files: a seed or input network as an edgelist, a nodelist, a recency table derived from a real-world network, and an out_degree table sampled from PubMed. Parameter values are passed to the SASCA-ReS code through a configuration file created by the user. Additional details on how to perform simulations are available from the Github repository. The configuration file requires 23 entries of which the first 11 control simulation at the environment level, the next 7 specify the characteristics of individual agents, and the remaining manage parallelism, logging, and the location of output files.

Unless otherwise mentioned, all simulations reported in this manuscript were performed on a compute cluster with up to 128 cores of parallelism and 512 GB of memory. Simulations were seeded with citation networks, Erdős-Rényi graphs, or lattice graphs with the fitness of seed nodes set to 1 in each case. A “standard” simulation refers to the Stahl-Johnstone seed set (above in Data) being allowed to grow for 30 years at a growth rate of 3% using 16 cores of parallelism, which would result in an output network of around 1.2 million nodes in the order of 3-4 minutes. The default environment refers to randomized (*ra*) phenotypes where preferential attachment weight (*pa_w*) and fitness_weight (*fit_w*) were assigned random values that summed to 1 for each agent and α was set to random values such that $0 \leq \alpha \leq 1$. Results from partially static agent environments were also conducted where either α or preferential weight was set to a fixed value for all agents. Note that fixing *pa_w* implicitly fixes *fit_w* since they sum to 1. For a subset of the experiments reported here, simulations were scaled to (i) 10-20 million nodes, (ii) 70-80 million nodes, and (iii) 100-250 million nodes.

2.4 Random Forest Analysis

A random forest regression analysis [39] was conducted to study model variables relative to time. This experiment was performed on the abm14 simulation where the final network size was 13,926,219 nodes and the simulation spanned 85 virtual years. A snapshot of node attributes for all agent nodes was recorded every 5 years, producing a total of 18 snapshots (including one from the final year of the simulation). For each snapshot, a random forest regressor was trained with Scikit Learn Python Library [40]. Each model consisted of 100 decision trees, with *max_features* = *n_features*

and no *max_depth* constraint; other hyperparameters were left at default values. The input features were publication year, the preferential attachment weight, fitness, and *out_degree*. The target variable was *in_degree* (number of citations received). We computed two types of feature importance: impurity-based feature importance (Supplementary Materials, S2) and permutation feature importance using the R^2 score. Feature importances were evaluated by examining empirical trends observed in the agent-based simulations to analyze SASCA-ReS model behavior. All models were trained on the Illinois Campus Cluster with up to 128 cores and 512GB of memory. The training scripts and analysis procedures are available in our Github repository [41].

2.5 Clustering Analysis

The abm14 network as well as variants of it were clustered using the Leiden algorithm optimizing the constant Potts model (Leiden-CPM) [42], with the number of iterations set to 2 and resolution values of either 0.1 or 0.01. Leiden-CPM at these resolutions did not complete on the larger abm76 and abm161 networks. Therefore, we used a two-stage approach as follows. First, we used a parallel Louvain implementation [43] on a machine with 64 cores, 950GB of RAM and a 4-hour time limit. If any resulting cluster exceeded 50M nodes, we reclustered with the parallel Louvain implementation. All Louvain clusters of size < 100 were then filtered out and the remainder were reclustered using Leiden-CPM with a resolution value of 0.0001 followed by post-processing for well-connectedness using the Connectivity Modifier [33] (Results and Supplementary Materials).

3 Results

In this section, we present results from experiments using SASCA-ReS that are designed to explore recency modeling, scalability, the relative importance of model variables, community structure, and unconventional strategies to optimize citations to a document in a citation network.

3.1 Recency Modeling

A salient feature of citation behavior is recency or immediacy [5], the tendency of authors to cite more contemporary articles than older ones.

In earlier versions of our simulator (SASCA-s and PyABM), high *in_degree* nodes in a seed graph had an advantage in accumulating citations [44, pg5 and Fig. 1] on account of preferential attachment overriding recency. In SASCA-ReS, we improved recency modeling through a binning approach, which can be tuned to recency patterns of different fields. Our choice of bin size is derived from the biomedical literature using the *cen* network (Materials and Methods). The effectiveness of this approach is shown in Fig. 1, where the proportion of citations made to preceding year nodes is more closely aligned with real-world data than in the case of the SASCA-s and PyABM models. The settings in Fig. 1 were used for all simulations reported in this manuscript.

Fig. 1 SASCA-ReS improves recency modeling. Here we show the true recency distribution (real-world data) for comparison with observed recency distributions using SASCA-ReS, SASCA-s, and PyABM. For all models shown, the simulation was performed for 30 years at a growth rate of 3% using the *sj* seedset in a randomized agent environment. For SASCA-ReS, recency bins (Materials and Methods) were set to single-year bins with bin i containing all publications from i years ago for the first ten years, followed by 5-year bins until year 51. Those articles that were published at least 51 years ago were assigned to the last bin.

3.2 Scalability

To establish the scalability of SASCA-ReS, we simulated the growth of citation networks at three different scales: (i) 10-20 million nodes, (ii) 50-100 million nodes, and (iii) greater than 100 million nodes. These simulations were conducted in the default environment, *ra*, where the citation phenotype of agents was randomized to represent a distribution of citation behaviors. These scales were chosen because of the availability of comparable real-world citation networks, although the *oa* real-world network is only about 70% as large as the *abm161* network while the *abm14* and *abm76* networks are much more closely matched in size.

In the first and second cases, the simulated networks comprised 13,926,219 nodes (*abm14*) and 75,598,213 nodes (*abm76*) respectively (Table 2 and Figure 2). In the third case, also a metaphor for the growth of the scientific literature from 1665-2025 (see Introduction), the resultant graph (*abm161*) network consisted of 160,714,032 nodes. These simulated networks are less sparse than the real-world examples they were compared against, which we attribute to incompleteness in the data for our real-world networks and our generative model.

Unsurprisingly, the software tools that we typically use to analyze networks do not scale well to the two larger networks (*abm76* and *abm161*). While it is possible to compute node and edge counts and degree distributions, it is expensive to compute metrics such as diameter and clustering coefficients, and even more challenging to cluster these networks. While this finding underscores an opportunity to develop more

Fig. 2 Scalable simulations of citation networks. Synthetic citation networks were generated with SASCA-ReS at three different scales (the count of nodes for the synthetic networks is approximately 161M, 76M and 14M). Real-world networks are shown for comparison. *Left:* Frequency of each in_degree. *Right:* Cumulative distribution function of in_degree.

scalable tools, it also restricted much of our analysis to networks at the 10-20 million node scale exemplified by the abm14 network.

Since the original submission of this article, we have developed a two-stage clustering approach (Materials and Methods), which has enabled clustering the abm76 and abm161 networks. However, it is still computationally expensive to analyze the larger networks and the approach merits further evaluation, so we have placed these initial findings in Supplementary Materials (S3).

3.3 Model variables

For the abm14 network, we first examined how the in_degree accumulated by agents at the end of a simulation varies according to when the agent was created (Figure 3). Agents that are created earlier in the simulation tend to have higher in_degree compared to those created later, likely even with recency being enforced since the agents created later have fewer years to accumulate citations in.

Examining the profiles of agents in the top 0.1% for in_degree (4,188–260,404 citations) in this simulation, the median values for out_degree and fitness amount to 103 and 18 respectively. Further, 92.04% of the agents in the top 0.1% have out_degree or fitness at least that of these medians. We evaluated observations in the top 0.1% of agents by in_degree where out_degree > 103 *or* fitness > 18, and noted sensitivity and specificity of 0.926 and 0.948 respectively. These data strongly suggest that out_degree and fitness of an agent are influential, which is also consistent with our previous observations using the PyABM model [44]. In contrast, the median value

of `pa_weight` was marginally different from the expected value of 0.5. However, the roughly 7.4% of agents in the false negative group suggest additional determinants in these stochastic simulations.

Fig. 3 Positional measures of `in_degree` for the `abm14m` network. The plot shows the median, third quartile, 90th and 99th percentile as well as the maximum `in_degree` for agents grouped by year in which they were created for the 85-year simulation that generated the `abm14m` network.

We also examined the cumulative distribution function (CDF) for `in_degree` under different conditions (Figure 4) and observed that a high α value of 0.95 caused an appreciable right shift of the CDF, indicating a redistribution of citations towards nodes of higher degree. Conversely, a low α value caused a corresponding left shift relative to the default randomized conditions. Altering the `pa_weight` of agents did not result in appreciable differences relative to the default simulations.

Last, we used a Random Forest regressor to infer the relative importance of fitness, `out_degree`, `pa_weight`, and publication year (Figure 5). Across simulation years, the permutation feature importances (PFI) stabilize during the course of the simulation, suggesting that once the dataset becomes sufficiently large, random forest models capture the underlying relationships with some consistency. Fitness consistently emerges as the dominant predictor while `out_degree` and publication year are also influential in making predictions. In contrast, preferential attachment weight exhibits lower importance for predictive accuracy.

3.4 Community Structure

An expected feature of growing citation networks is the emergence of community structure, which has previously been reported in agent-based simulations initiated on an epistemic grid [31]. To explore whether networks generated under SASCA-ReS exhibit community structure, we attempted to cluster them.

Fig. 4 In-degree CDF on 14m node networks. Here we show the CDF plots of in-degrees from six different simulations where different agent parameters were static.

Fig. 5 Permutation feature importances for abm14. Here we show the permutation feature importances, measured with R^2 score, of random forest regressors trained on abm14 datasets at 5-year intervals during the simulation. Each random forest regressor consisted of 100 decision trees and predicts the final citation count received by an agent using four features: fitness, out_degree, preferential attachment weight, and publication year. Fitness is a dominant feature.

While we have previously clustered the real-world Open Citations network of size 75,025,194 (Table 2) with the Leiden algorithm optimizing the Constant Potts model, the allocations of time and memory needed to analyze the abm76 and variants of it generated by varying parameter settings exceeded what was available to us. Further, clustering the abm76 and abm14 networks with the parallelized implementation of the Louvain algorithm [45] available as an extension to the Kuzu graph database [43]

	Min	Q1	Median	Q3	Max
abm161	254	536	2,389	5,965	81,675,241
abm76	678	8,051	4,181,752	13,781,060	44,347,046
abm14	1,016,079	1,948,065	3,162,148	4,719,101	6,679,698

Table 3 Clustering with the Louvain algorithm. All three networks were clustered using an implementation of the Louvain algorithm. Summary statistics for the size of non-singleton clusters are shown.

resulted in a decidedly unsatisfying cluster size distribution (Table 3) with the largest cluster comprising 51%, 58%, and 48% of the network for the abm161, abm76 and abm14 networks respectively. We do not consider these single-pass Louvain clusterings very useful for evaluating community structure in these larger networks.

agent phenotype	Min	Q1	Median	Q3	Max	num clusters	node cov.	sing.
alpha0.05	2	15	16	21	4714	569,362	1.00	20,647
alpha0.95	2	66	102	147	2936	118,428	1.00	6181
pa0.05	2	30	43	61	3532	260,943	1.00	927
pa0.95	2	31	44	62	5576	264,911	1.00	685
ra	2	30	43	61	4117	263,438	1.00	746
ra_noalpha	2	13	13	16	5419	659,344	1.00	25,866
alpha0.05	2	5	5	7	528	2,117,329	1.00	5156
alpha0.95	2	8	16	29	379	675,401	0.99	106,358
pa0.05	2	6	9	15	350	1,212,845	1.00	34,110
pa0.95	2	6	9	15	392	1,214,029	1.00	51,955
ra	2	6	9	15	351	1,213,577	1.00	38,788
ra_noalpha	2	4	5	5	544	2,323,650	1.00	7631

Table 4 Effect of α on cluster sizes SASCA-ReS simulations were performed in random and static agent environments at a growth rate of 4.0125% for 85 years to generate networks of size 13,926,219 nodes. Each of these networks was then clustered with the Leiden algorithm optimizing the Constant Potts Model (CPM) with resolution values $r = 0.01$ (top) or $r = 0.1$ (bottom). The largest statistic (Q1, Median, and Q3) are boldfaced for each. *sing*: count of singleton clusters; *node cov.* rounded fraction of nodes in non-singleton clusters

In an alternate strategy, we used the Leiden algorithm optimizing the Constant Potts Model [42] at resolution values of 0.1 and 0.01 to generate more intuitively sensible [46] cluster size distributions from SASCA-ReS networks generated at the 10-20 million node scale under different conditions (Table 5). The results of this experiment are shown in Table 4 and indicate that a high α setting substantially increases the median, first and third quartile of cluster sizes relative to all other conditions tested while a high preferential weight setting results in the highest maximum cluster size. Additionally, high α setting increases the average local clustering coefficient (alcc) and values of positional statistics of in_degree except at the 99th percentile (Table 5) consistent with observations in (Figure 4).

We also examined the “age” of each cluster, where cluster age is defined as the number of years from the end of the simulation to the time the earliest node in the

abm14 variants	alcc	25th	median	75th	90th	99th
ra	0.0839	5	12	24	49	360
ra_noalpha	0.0239	3	7	14	33	489
alpha0.05	0.0212	3	7	15	34	502
pa0.05	0.0824	5	12	26	52	408
alpha0.95	0.1498	8	20	39	70	287
pa0.95	0.0883	4	11	22	43	295
alpha0.00	0.0054	3	7	14	34	505
alpha0.20	0.0530	4	9	18	39	446
alpha0.40	0.0807	4	11	23	45	370
alpha0.60	0.1052	6	14	28	52	321
alpha0.80	0.1296	7	17	34	61	294
alpha1.00	0.1605	8	21	42	75	294

Table 5 High α settings increase in_degree and average local clustering coefficient (alcc) of agent nodes. The pattern is reversed at the 99th percentile. Networks shown are variants of the abm14 network produced by varying α or preferential attachment weights. Summary statistics for different networks are shown for in_degree. Each network has 13,926,219 nodes. ra: randomized background where α and preferential attachment weight are randomized; ra_noalpha randomized: agent background with α switched off. For the remaining networks, either alpha is fixed and pa.w randomized or the converse.

cluster was created. We observed a pronounced decrease in the size of agent-only clusters in the high α simulation as cluster-age increases. Finally, we examined, under varying conditions, the relationship between the size of clusters that consisted only of agents and their age (Figure 6). To further examine the effect of α , we also examined node coverage (the fraction of the network in clusters of size at least 2 or at least 10) across two different resolution values as α is varied.

We conjecture from these results that α has several effects. Increasing α (greater insularity) causes a redistribution of citations that results in more nodes of high degree when compared to a randomized (ra) background. Second that higher α settings favor community structure—the formation of citation dense regions in the network. In contrast, the high preferential attachment condition outcompetes high α in terms of generating maximum cluster size but trails at other positional measures shown. Of interest also is that many clusters are agent-only, suggesting that such regions do not require seed nodes and that clusters likely form around nodes of high fitness. Last that the older clusters are larger when α is high. Extrapolating to the real-world, α allows modeling of insularity in citation behavior, which can reasonably be expected of research communities.

3.5 Mavericks

The use of citation counts to evaluate productivity and impact is an incentive to being well-cited. Results from PyABM suggest that high-referencing may supplement epistemic quality [25]. To explore unconventional strategies that might result in high

Fig. 6 Effect of α on cluster age. Boxplots showing the distribution of cluster sizes produced by Leiden-CPM 0.01 when α or preferential attachment weight is varied. *ra*: randomize background; *ra_noalpha*: randomized background with α switched off (agents select targets from within the 2-hop neighborhood)

in_degree for individual agents, we created customized agents that we refer to as mavericks. Mavericks follow a different rule set than the agents in SASCA-ReS and may cite any other node in the network. Further, a maverick is not controlled by α . Each maverick is assigned a fitness value x and an out_degree quota y , which we vary.

Three different types of mavericks were designed: a *maximizer* that scans the entire network and randomly cites y random nodes from the top 0.1% of the network by total degree; a *randomnik* that scans the entire network and selects y random nodes; and a *minimizer* agent that scans the entire network and selects y random nodes (out_degree) from the bottom 0.1% of the network by total degree. Mavericks were created in the first year of the simulation and were assigned the same fitness level and out_degree quota. For the maverick parameters, we varied x from 1, 10, 100, and 1000 and y between 10 and 249. Given randomness in the SASCA-ReS model, we planted three mavericks of each type per simulation. Additionally, we designated three non-maverick agents per simulation as controls.

Simulations were conducted for 30 years at a growth rate of 3% using the *sj* seed set where the nodes exhibit varying in_degree that varies from 0 – 88, 435 produced a wide range of in_degree for mavericks to select from. The results (Figure 7) show that: (i) increasing fitness of mavericks increases their resultant in_degree, (ii) increasing

the out_degree of mavericks increases their in_degree, and (iii) the maximizer maverick outcompetes the randomnik, which in turn outcompetes the minimizer.

We also computed disruption [47] for mavericks and control agents and observed that when $y = 249$, the maximizer maverick although very well-cited had disruption values considerably lower than the randomnik, minimizer, or control. We attribute this to the larger denominator in the case of the maverick on account of its references also being highly cited (Supplemental Materials, S3). Thus, the original disruption formula of Wu and colleagues [47] may not be optimal for measuring disruption in mavericks and a variant [48, 49] might be more informative.

Fig. 7 Maverick citation strategies. Three each of *maximizer* (max), *randomnik* (rnd), and *minimizer* (min) mavericks were planted in the first year of 30-year 3% growth simulation on the *sj* seed network with randomized agent phenotypes. A *control* group of three randomized agent was also planted. Simulations in the upper row were performed with all planted agents (mavericks and controls) assigned out_degree quotas of 249 publications versus an out_degree of 10 in the bottom row. In independent experiments, mavericks and controls were assigned fitness values of 1, 10, 100, and 1000 (columns).

4 Discussion

Using the SASCA-ReS model, which features improved recency modeling, we modeled the growth of citation networks at scale. Models do not generate conclusive evidence but are useful for stimulating new ideas, revisiting existing ones, and generating new hypotheses. The SASCA-ReS simulations reported here suggest that fitness and `out_degree` are influential. While SASCA-ReS does not consider journal or author reputation, the effects of collaboration between authors, the limitations of peer review, and epistemic misconduct, the result suggests that quality is important even in a complex environment of individual behaviors. The `out_degree` effect is consistent with Small, Sweeney, and Greenlee’s interpretation in 1984 [50] of ‘high-referencing’ articles and the case for fractional citation counting.

Simulations were conducted in randomized agent environments corresponding to our assumption of a broad variety of citation behaviors across individuals. Networks generated under the SASCA-ReS model are denser than the real-world examples we used for comparison. While we cannot exclude an artifact of the model, we are inclined to believe that data quality (missing nodes and edges) may also account for this difference. All citations made by agents are to nodes in the growing network, whereas publications in the comparable real-world network may cite or be cited by articles that are not included in the network. Thus, the simulated networks will have more edges and hence be denser than their corresponding real-world networks.

Simulations enable asking counterfactual questions. We asked what the structure of the global citation network might be today if researchers had historically exhibited extreme insularity, modeled by high α values, in their citation behavior. The results suggest that the network would shift towards community structure, perhaps at the cost of interdisciplinary work.

Using maverick agents, we examined the hypothetical of whether discipline-independent citations would favor the accumulation of citations to individual documents. We observed that referencing only the most highly cited nodes in a network results in very high citations. In the real-world, this effect is likely counterbalanced by the insular behavior of researchers. What is more interesting is whether some degree of maverick behavior is prevalent and can be distinguished from more benign motivations.

These initial studies were limited by the inability to study synthetic networks of over 75 million nodes in detail because of software and infrastructure constraints. That fitness is a driver, even in our idealized environment, makes a welcome case for quality in the world of citations. The result from the maximizer maverick suggests that more cynical strategies may also work.

Our emphasis on model simplification in this manuscript limited the extent to which we could explore the nonlinearity of citation dynamics proposed by Golosovsky [19]. Finally, we have not assessed statistical identifiability, but we expect that different parameter settings in SASCA-ReS could generate the same emergent properties.

At this point in the development history of our project, we are slightly relaxing our emphasis on idealized models and have developed an initial prototype (SASCA-ResA) that replaces the one-author:one-paper feature in SASCA-ReS with a more complex multi-author design [51]. We anticipate making interpretations from using both models together.

Supplementary information. This manuscript is accompanied by Supplementary Information in pdf format.

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Declarations

- This study was partially supported by the Illinois:Insper Partnership and NSF Award 2402559
- The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.
- Data availability. Data for the large networks generated in this study are available from the Illinois Data Bank under IDB-9265079 [52]. All other data are publicly available or can be regenerated through the protocols in the manuscript and the SASCA-ReS Code.
- Code availability The code and documentation for SASCA-ReS is available from Github [36].
- Author contributions: Conceptualization (GC, MP, TW), Data Curation (MP), Formal Analysis (MP, HY, MP), Investigation (MP, HY, TW, GC), Methodology (MP, GC, TW), Supervision (GC, TW), Validation (MP, HY, GC), Visualization (HY, MP, GC), Writing- original draft (GC, TW, MP, HY), Writing- Review and Editing (GC, TW, MP, HY), Funding acquisition (GC, TW).

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